

The Role of Forensic Accounting to Enhancing the Efficiency of the Accounting Information System to Dealing with Financial Crises

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Abstract: The study aimed to investigate the role of forensic accounting in enhancing the efficiency of accounting systems within the Sudanese banking sector, particularly in the context of the financial crisis precipitated by the war that began on April 15 and the subsequent damage to banking infrastructure. The research seeks to explore how forensic accounting can assist banking systems in managing the crisis, mitigating associated risks, and facilitating recovery efforts. Additionally, it assesses the impact of forensic accounting on the effectiveness of accounting information systems in Sudanese banks by surveying professional opinions and analyzing the experience of the Bank of Khartoum. Utilizing both descriptive and quantitative deductive methodologies, the study employed a structured questionnaire to collect data and evaluate the opinions of the intended sample. The study found several significant outcomes, including a positive and statistically significant relationship between forensic accounting and the efficiency of accounting information systems. The data indicates that forensic accounting effectively enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of accounting systems, particularly through its impact on system quality (SQ) and service quality (QS). Forensic accounting contributes by providing predictive and confirmatory information that meets stakeholder needs, producing valuable reports, and supporting continuous updates to financial and accounting systems. Moreover, forensic accounting plays a crucial role in improving the efficiency of accounting information systems in managing financial crises. The study highlights that forensic accounting is instrumental in two key phases of crisis management: containment and damage reduction (FCM-CDR) and recovery and restoration of activity post-crisis (FCM-RRA). Also, the study revealed a notable deficiency in the implementation of forensic accounting practices within the banking sector, which is the focus of this research. Despite a relatively high level of awareness regarding forensic accounting, its practical application remains underdeveloped.

Keywords: Forensic Accounting, Accounting Information Systems, Financial Crisis, Bank of Khartoum

I. INTRODUCTION

The continuation of sustainable growth relies heavily on the stability and advancement of economic systems, with the banking system being one of the most critical components. Operating in an increasingly dynamic and risk-laden environment, the banking sector is inherently intertwined with financial crises, which have become a fundamental risk factor. As a result, banking systems are continuously enhancing their infrastructures to defend against both current and potential financial crises, while also improving their management practices. Information systems, particularly accounting information systems, are considered one of the core pillars on which banks depend. These systems play a crucial role in reducing uncertainty, bolstering confidence in decision-making processes, and addressing crises by mitigating their impacts and enabling the possibility of resolving them before or during their occurrence. To effectively fulfill this role, accounting information systems must provide accurate and timely information to all levels of management, equipping them to respond to financial and banking crises more effectively.

To enhance the efficiency of these systems, the researcher seeks to explore the potential of using forensic accounting to strengthen the accounting information system in managing the financial crises that have severely impacted the Sudanese financial and banking sector following the war that erupted on April 15, 2023. This conflict, which led to the widespread destruction of banking infrastructure in Khartoum—the central hub of Sudan's banking system, including the Central Bank of Sudan, the financial and banking sector, the Khartoum Stock Exchange, and the Insurance Supervisory Authority—has significantly worsened the ongoing humanitarian crisis and exacerbated the

severe cash liquidity crisis. The situation is expected to deteriorate further if the conflict persists, as evidenced by the looting of customers' savings and banking assets (ACAPS Thematic Report: Sudan, 2023)¹. Concerns remain regarding the capacity of accounting information systems to withstand the prolonged effects of the war, given the unprecedented scale of disruption in the Sudanese banking environment since the country's independence.

A. THE STUDY PROBLEM:

This paper seeks to explore the role of forensic accounting in enhancing the efficiency of accounting information systems in managing the current financial crisis and mitigating the associated risks. It also seeks to identify mechanisms for crisis recovery in the face of unexpected disruptions to information technology systems caused by force majeure events, such as power outages, instability, security challenges, and the ongoing war. Specifically, the study explores the development of disaster recovery strategies, including the restoration of damaged or destroyed databases, a task that most Sudanese banks have failed to accomplish. An exception is the Bank of Khartoum, which successfully resumed operations immediately after the outbreak of the conflict, demonstrating its ability to effectively manage the crisis and recover its data in a timely manner.²

To achieve the objectives of this study, the following research questions are formulated:

- Is there an effective role for forensic accounting in enhancing the efficiency of the accounting information system in the banking sector?
- Does forensic accounting contribute to improving the efficiency of the accounting information system AIS (system quality and service quality) to contain the damage resulting from financial crises (containment or damage reduction)?
- Does forensic accounting contribute to improving the efficiency of the accounting information system AIS (system quality and service quality) to restore activity after financial crises (recovery and restoration of activity)?
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B. OBJECTIVES AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY:

The study aims to examine the role of forensic accounting in enhancing the efficiency of accounting systems to improve the effectiveness of the banking sector amid the Sudanese financial crises, particularly the war that began on April 15 and the subsequent destruction of banking infrastructure. The study seeks to explore how forensic accounting can assist accounting and banking systems in managing this crisis, mitigating the associated risks, and facilitating recovery efforts. Additionally, it aims to assess the impact of forensic accounting on the effectiveness of accounting information systems in Sudanese banks by surveying professional opinions and analyzing the experience of the Bank of Khartoum, specifically focusing on the relationship between forensic accounting skills and their contribution to enhancing information system efficiency during financial crises. The study also seeks to determine the extent to which forensic accounting is utilized and applied within the Sudanese banking systems under investigation.

C. RESEARCH GAP:

Many studies have explored the relationship between accounting information systems and financial crises from various perspectives and dimensions. However, this research seeks to focus on a distinct set of dimensions that shape this relationship. Specifically, the study emphasizes two key dimensions of the accounting information system: system

¹ - Relief Web Blog, ACAPS Thematic report: Sudan - Implications of financial blockages in Sudan, 11 August 2023, available on line at: <https://2u.pw/W7pFYIs>

² - Report - Magdy Qarnas - newspaper article - Al-Rakbwa electronic newspaper - citation 11/16/2023.

<https://www.alrakoba.net/31849328/%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A8%D9%86%D9%88%D9%83-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%88%D8%AF%D8%A7%D9%86%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D9%88%D9%85%D8%A3%D8%B2%D9%82-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AD%D8%B1%D8%A8>

quality and quality of service. For the financial crisis variable, the study concentrates on two critical aspects—Containment/Damage Reduction during the crisis, and Recovery, Restoration of activity. The primary objective is to investigate the potential role of forensic accounting, from the perspective of banking professionals, in enhancing the efficiency of accounting systems in managing financial crises. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no previous study has integrated forensic accounting, accounting information systems, and financial crises in this manner. Additionally, the study addresses a significant research gap by examining the financial crisis triggered by the ongoing war and its implications for the Sudanese banking sector. The Bank of Khartoum remains the central focus, as it is one of the key institutions that successfully absorbed the initial shock of the crisis and restored its operations amid the unfolding conflict.

D. RESEARCH MODEL

This model was developed to achieve the study's objectives based on previous studies, as it aims to clarify the potential relationship of the study's variables and explain the impact of forensic accounting (FOA) and its role in improving the efficiency of accounting information systems (AIS), as well as the impact of that in dealing with the financial crisis under consideration. The model also describes the investigation of accounting information systems (AIS) as an independent variable, which is why the dimensions of financial crisis management in Sudan appear as the dependent variable of this study.

Figure 1. The research Model

E. DEFINITION OF STUDY DIMENSIONS:

1- Forensic Accounting (FOA):

Forensic accounting is one of the specialist disciplines in the field of accounting knowledge that has advanced skills with diverse dimensions in the field of investigations and detection of tampering and fraudulent cases, as well as specialized legal and accounting dimensions. Many definitions and meanings attempt to explain forensic accounting, as Manning G. A. (2010) defines “forensic accounting as the combination of accounting, auditing and investigation skills to a standard that is acceptable by a court of jurisdiction to address issues in dispute in the context of civil and criminal litigation”. Forensic accounting is also viewed as the practice of applying specialized knowledge to evidence of economic transactions and reporting appropriate for the purpose of establishing accountability or valuation of administrative proceedings, as well as the utilization of accounting, auditing, and investigative skills to assist in legal issues, (Adewumi, B., & Toluyemi, T.2000, Wells, 2003 :Houck et al., 2006; Bassey & Ahonkhai, 2017:57). It also works to cover many factors such as: exhaustive investigation and comprise fraud examination, complete diligence evaluations and risk assessment, detection of financial statement deception, cybercrimes, and unlawful money transfers. (Smith & Crumbley, 2009, Okoye & Gbegi, 2013).

2- Accounting Information System Dimensions:

- a) **System quality (SQ):** The quality of the system expresses the qualities and features that the information system includes. (Dalloul et al., 2022; Al-Okaily et al., 2020; Al Jaberi & Qawasmeh, 2020; Alabaddi et al., 2020; Aldegis, 2018; DeLone & McLean, 2002).

- b) **Quality of Service (QS):** It is an indicator of the actual quality of service, including the delivery of a prompt, relevant, dependable, and appropriate service that influences the user's utilization and contentment with the information system. (Dalloul et al., 2022; Putra & Setiawan, 2020; Tam & Oliveira, 2016).

3- **Financial Crises Dimensions (FCM) :**

- a) **Containment/Damage Reduction (CDR)** Are the set of activities through which the pre-prepared plans are activated and implemented to confront the crisis and translate preparations into real action to contain the crisis and reduce its damages, including the use of all efforts, resources and means possible to achieve this (Aljuhmani & Emeagwali, 2017; Aloun & Attieh, 2018; Alpaslan & Mitroff, 2021; Alradie, 2011; King III, 2007).
- b) **Recovery and Restoration of Activity (RRC):** The set of activities that activates and implements crisis recovery and recuperation strategies. This includes taking activities and making judgments that facilitate the successful resumption of regular activity. Additional responsibilities include identifying and determining the extent of the crisis's effects and damage, identifying the actual requirements for dealing with the crisis's repercussions and effects, activating communication channels, and raising awareness about the severity of the crisis and treatment plans. (Dalloul et al., 2022).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW:

The success of any organization is linked to the success of the information systems used. Information is the basic pillar of the operations of these organizations and dealing with all the circumstances surrounding the life cycle of the organizations' success, especially in light of fluctuations and financial crises. Since information is the main product of these systems in crisis management, it must be distinguished these systems are efficient and effective in producing this information. Accounting information systems are considered one of the most important systems without which financial and economic institutions cannot work, especially banking institutions, it is necessary for them to work on improving this system continuously and make it work efficiently to increase its ability to withstand economic fluctuations and financial crises and follow up on the changes that occur in the environment. And make decisions. Where efficient systems have the effective ability to manage crises before, during, and after they occur (Al-Hayaly, A.M2011), (Hanna, et al.2018), (Dalloul, et al.2023).

We will review previous literature through the variables of the study, in which we will address the dimensions of the efficiency of the accounting information system in its ability to deal with financial crises, as follows:

A- **System Quality (SQ) and Financial Crisis Management (FCM- SQ)**

To learn about the roles played by accounting information systems in dealing with financial crises and how to manage them, through the dimension of system quality in the banking sector, Zwyalif (2015) and Al-Hayaly (2011), indicated that system quality has an essential role in crisis management and is more influential in the preparedness and prevention phase and the damage containment phase. We also find that the quality of the system stems from its characteristics. Bushra (2017) indicated that the characteristics of management information systems and its equipment have an impact on crisis management in economic institutions. Alzoubi (2020) also emphasized that the characteristics of management information systems play an important role in improving the ability of banks to deal with crises and manage them effectively. As Adwan (2019), Ahmed and Jabbar (2021) revealed the vital role that system quality plays in enhancing crisis management with its tasks and operations in many sectors, Daham et al. (2020) also emphasized. That there are critical roles for management information systems in the banking sector in its awareness of financial crises through preparation, prevention, damage containment, and recovery. Abdul Razzaq (2011) also found that accounting information systems have an important role in confronting crises, improving companies' ability to deal with crises.

B- **Quality of Service - Financial Crisis Management (QS-FCM)**

The quality of services is a critical dimension of information system quality, particularly in the context of accounting information systems. Al-Hayaly (2011) emphasized that the quality of banking information systems is

pivotal in managing crises. He also highlighted the importance of service quality, including the personal attributes of system managers and employees, as a crucial factor in effective crisis management. Supporting this, Adwan (2019) demonstrated the relationship between the effectiveness of management information systems and crisis management in the public sector, underscoring the significance of service quality in improving crisis management across the stages of pre-crisis, during-crisis, and post-crisis. In contrast, Gopinathan and Raman (2020) examined the role of various information system quality factors—including information quality, system quality, service quality, and communication systems—in emergency operations management. Their findings indicated that service quality had no significant impact on the emergency management process, presenting a nuanced perspective on its role in crisis response.

C- Forensic Accounting

As noted by Akinbowale et al. (2023). In his study on the impact of applying forensic accounting techniques to mitigate fraud risks, he discovered a positive relationship between the risks of banking fraud and forensic accounting, as well as an association, albeit limited, between ineffective forensic technique application and some fraud incidents. According to Yang, C. H., and Lee, K. C. (2020), forensic accounting is focused on managing fraud risk. That is, it permits the assessment of all organizational risks, including fraud risk. Emmanuel, O. G., et al. (2018) discovered that forensic accounting approaches contribute to the integrity of financial data by preventing fraud.

Regarding the role that forensic accounting plays in enhancing the accounting information system, Emmanuel, O. G., et al. (2018) stated that the focus of forensic accounting is on both evidence of economic transactions and report preparation. It also improves the role of the accounting system's internal control system in reducing fraudulent activities and reporting cases of financial statement distortion.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

An exploratory study was conducted to confirm the study's purpose by investigating the opinions of the study sample at Bank of Khartoum and its branches through the (intentional) sampling method to obtain specific opinions, about the role of forensic accounting in enhancing the effectiveness of the accounting information system to managing financial crises. The study utilized a descriptive-analytical approach, along with various statistical tools, to analyze the data collected from the intended population. The following methodology were employed to achieve the objectives:

A- Design of the study sample:

The study sample consists of employees from the Bank of Khartoum (BOK), recognized as one of the leading banks in Sudan. The BOK Group employs approximately 3,000 individuals and operates over 150 branches and cash offices, as well as more than 325 ATMs and CDMs, representing the largest branch and ATM network in the country. BOK is the largest provider of banking services in Sudan and is progressively expanding its offerings, including mobile payments. During the recent crisis, the Bank of Khartoum succeeded in maintaining operations due to its preparedness, having implemented alternative solutions to manage potential crises. One of the most effective alternatives was the use of financial technology in the banking sector, including mobile money transfers, mobile payments, and electronic banking applications. However, these systems experienced frequent disruptions due to weaknesses in communication networks, internet outages, and power cuts. A critical factor contributing to the bank's resilience is its comprehensive business continuity and disaster recovery plan (Siddig, 2023).

The success of the Bank of Khartoum can be attributed to its mobile banking application, (Bankak), developed in 2014, which has become one of Sudan's largest fintech platforms. The app currently serves over seven million users, with numbers continuing to rise. Since the outbreak of the war, there has been an 85% increase in app activations, as reported by Fadl Mohamed Khair, chair of the bank's board of directors, to (The New Humanitarian). This growth has paved the way for other fintech innovations such as) My Cash) and) Rittal Pay) —mobile digital wallets that do not require formal bank accounts, helping to democratize access to fintech services (Hipa Salih, 2024).

Table 1: Demographic Statistic

Demographic Factors	Count	Percentage
<i>Education</i>		
Bachelor's degree	91	35.80
Higher Diploma	12	4.70
Master's degree	63	24.80
PhD	46	18.10
Other	42	16.50
Total	254	100
<i>Scientific specialization</i>		
Accounting	90	35.43
Forensic Accounting	0	0.00
Economic	51	20.08
Management	79	31.10
Other	34	13.39
Total	254	100
<i>Job Positions</i>		
Branch Manager	43	16.93
Head of a Department	97	38.19
Auditor	52	20.47
Systems analyst.	62	24.41
Forensic accountant	0	0.00
Total	254	100
<i>Operating years (Bank Age)</i>		
5. - 10	67	26.38
10. - 15	115	45.28
15 - 20	38	14.96
20 - 25	19	7.48
MOER THAN 25	15	5.91
Total	254	100

Source: Survey data

B- Selection Criteria for Respondents:

The study commenced by outlining the characteristics and criteria for selecting respondents. The sample consisted of employees from the bank, specifically targeting individuals in key positions, as their responses are expected to provide more meaningful insights related to the study's variables. See Table (1).

I- Justifications for Respondent Selection:

1. Respondents should possess experience or knowledge pertinent to forensic accounting and financial crises.
2. Respondents should hold roles that involve significant engagement with accounting information systems or financial crisis management.
3. Respondents must have a working knowledge of forensic accounting practices and their application in financial crises.

II- Selected Positions Included:

- Branch Managers
- Department Heads
- Forensic Accountants
- Systems Analysts
- Auditors

The study focused on an intentional sample, as detailed by Khalid, W. E. O. et al. (2024), shown in Table 1. One of the most notable observations from analyzing the opinions of the study sample is that none of the participants work in or specialize in forensic accounting.

C - Data Collection Methods:

Data were collected using a questionnaire specifically designed for this study, which was deemed the most appropriate method given the ongoing war in Sudan and the scarcity of available data on forensic accounting. The content of the questionnaire was based by previous studies and the theoretical framework. It consisted of seven main sections, comprising 29 items that addressed the study's dimensions and hypotheses (see Table 2). Each item was measured using a five-point Likert scale (Likert, 1932), ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) (Khalid, W. E. O., 2020; Khalid, W. E., et al., 2024).

The researcher adapted five items related to forensic accounting from Elseed and Khalid, W. E. O. (2021), and Kinda R. et al. (2022). Additionally, eight items concerning the accounting information system, based on the selected dimensions of the study, were drawn from Inaam Al-Zwyalif (2015), Alabaddi, Z. A. et al. (2020), and Dalloul et al. (2023). Eight items focusing on financial crises were also adapted from Dalloul et al. (2023). Furthermore, eight items were developed to explore the relationship between forensic accounting, accounting information systems, and financial crises, adapted from Dalloul et al. (2023) and Alabaddi, Z. A. et al. (2020). The questionnaire was distributed to the intended sample and remained available for four months, beginning in December 2023. An electronic questionnaire link was shared with employees of the BOK Group via semi-official channels, including WhatsApp groups, Facebook, LinkedIn, the BOK website's "Contact Us" section, and through personal connections with friends working at the bank. A total of 254 completed questionnaires were collected, which is considered a reasonably sufficient sample size given the challenges that affected achieving the target response rate. These challenges included:

- Intermittent internet disruptions
- Many branches are out of service.
- Communication outages in certain regions
- Psychological distress experienced by employees due to the ongoing war
- Job instability among bank employees (Darfur 24- The Khartoum Bank administration)³.

Table: 2: Variables and Reliability

Variables	Dimension	Items	Mean	St. d	Reliabilities Cronbach's Alpha
FOA	FOA	5	3.712	1.44328	0.769
	SQ	4	3.974	0.57111	0.754
AIS	QS	4	3.196	1.15934	0.701
	FOA&AIS	3	4.004	1.08329	0.718
FCM	CDR	4	3.792	0.65966	0.731
	RRA	4	3.765	0.91995	0.763
	FOA&FCM	3	3.587	1.30613	0.709

Source: Survey data, SPSS V23 -2024

The findings detailed in Table (2) reveal the reliability coefficients for the study variables' dimensions, along with the corresponding means and standard deviations. All coefficients exceeded the hypothesized reliability benchmark of 0.5, indicating robust reliability. Additionally, the table outlines the number of items for each axis of the questionnaire, with most axes containing four items, except for the first axis, which comprises five. Some axes were reduced to three items due to the exclusion of certain statements following factor analysis, as these items did not produce reliable results. Despite this, the values presented in the table are deemed satisfactory and appropriate for the study.

The descriptive statistical analysis of the responses from the study sample highlights a notable deficiency in the implementation of forensic accounting practices within the banking sector, particularly at the Bank of Khartoum,

³- Darfur 24- 14,Des, 2023, <https://www.darfur24.com/2023/12/14/%D8%A8%D9%86%D9%83->

the focus of this research. Despite a relatively high level of awareness regarding forensic accounting, its practical application remains underdeveloped. This aligns with the conclusions drawn by Kinda R. et al. (2022), further emphasizing the gap between knowledge and practice in this field.

C - Hypotheses:

- ✓ **H.1:** Forensic Accounting is an effective tool for improving the efficiency of the accounting information system in the banking sector.
- ✓ **H.2:** Forensic Accounting contributes to improving the efficiency of AIS (system quality, quality of service) to contain the damage resulting from financial crises (containment/damage reduction).
- ✓ **H.3:** Forensic Accounting contributes to improving the efficiency of AIS (system quality and service quality) to restore activity after financial crises (recovery and restoration of activity).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

a) Measurement Sample Testing:

To assess the reliability and validity of the obtained sample, Cronbach's Alpha was calculated for all factors, yielding a value of 0.794, as shown in Table 3. This exceeds the minimum threshold of 0.7 recommended by Nunnally (1978) and Peterson (1994) for establishing scale reliability. Subsequently, confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to verify the convergent validity of the measurement items, in line with the guidelines provided by Anderson and Gerbin (1998), Bagozzi and Foxall (1996), and Suleiman et al. (2021), as seen in Table 3.

Table: 3: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.749
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	6259.289
	df	378
	Sig.	.000

Source: Survey data, SPSS V23 -2024

For checking sampling adequacy, Kaiser-Meyer-Oklin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of Spherity were performed. The value of KMO (0.749) and Bartlett's test of Spherity ($\chi^2 = 6259.289$, $df = 378$ and $p \leq 0.000$) represented the adequacy of sampling for further analysis. The data was analyzed using principal axis factoring and promax with Kaiser Normalization rotation method. Seven factors were identified. These Seven factors were labeled as FOA-SQ - QS - FOA&AIS- CDR- RRA and FOA&FCM.

b) Factor Analysis

Factor Analysis (FA) is a simple variate technique for analyzing the structure of interrelationships among a large number of variables by defining sets of variables that are highly interrelated. MOHAMMED, E. M. E, et al (2022), Tavakol, M., & Wetzel, A. (2020). "Confirmatory factor analysis" was executed to examine the discriminant validity of the variables of this study. Factor analysis was performed with 1 as the Eigen value to improve the strength of the factors. From this analysis, two items associated with the study dimensions were removed owing to factor loadings of less than 0.40 or cross loadings. Table 5 shows the Rotated Component Matrix of factors by Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization., which shows the saturation of the factors and the extent of the correlation of the variables after the development process, which Rotation converged in 8 iterations, also the table showed that there is independence in the correlation between the variables, which indicates the validity of the analysis.

Table 4: Rotated Pattern Matrix^a

	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Q10	.853						
Q12	.809						
Q7	.743						
Q15	.730						
Q9	.707						
Q2		.945					
Q24		.892					
Q5		.859					
Q27		.794					
Q19			.956				
Q16			.951				
Q17			.882				
Q6				.919			
Q23				.903			
Q4				.757			
Q3				.710			
Q18				.469			
Q8					.989		
Q13					.977		
Q21					.676		
Q26						.816	
Q28						.743	
Q25						.617	
Q22							.993
Q14							.721
Q20							.939

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.
 a. Rotation converged in 8 iterations.

c) Testing of Hypotheses and Finds:

To testing the validity of the study hypotheses and demonstrate the relationship between the variables, the following statistical analyzes were used:

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient:

Pearson correlation coefficient has been used in this study used to show the correlations and measure the level between the variables of the study, and to ascertain the extent to which independent variables exploited (Khalid, W. E. O.et al, 2024). Table (5) shows the correlation of study variables among them.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis between study variables;

Variables	Dimension	FA	SQ	QS	FAAIS	CDMM	RC	FAFC
FOA	FA	1						
	SQ	.042	1					
AIS	QS	-.324**	.565**	1				
	FOA&AIS	-.016	.333**	.574**	1			
FC	CDR	-.076	.318**	.609**	.727**	1		
	RRA	.730**	-.006	-.421**	-.124*	-.115	1	
	FOA&FCM	.565**	-.080	-.416**	-.376**	-.361**	.578**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey data, SPSS V23 -2024

An examination of the correlations between the independent and dependent variables reveals that all study variables are significantly related to one another.

Simple Regression

To testing the validity of the study hypotheses and demonstrate the relationship between the variables, Simple regression has been used in this study hypotheses to test the relationship levels (weak and strong), type of relationship (negative and positive), and significant level, standardized coefficient (β) value, un-standardized coefficient (β), Adjusted R Square (R²) Change R Square, Durbin-Watson (D.W), and F-Test value.

Testing First Hypothesis:

H.1: Forensic Accounting is an effective tool for improving the efficiency of the accounting information system in the banking sector.

Table 6: Test of Simple Regression between FOA & AIS Dimensions

FOA & AIS									
Variable	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Durbin-Watson	β eta	Sig	F Value	Sig
SQ	.522	.518	1.44488	.522	2.033	.542	.000	.440	.000
QS	.505	.501	1.36829	.505	1.994	-.514	.000	29.491	.000

Source: Survey data, SPSS V23 -2024

Table (6) showed the test and results of simple regression of the relationship between Forensic Accounting (FOA) and accounting information system (AIS) Dimension: there is positive and significant relationship between (FOA) and (AIS) dimensions, on the standardized coefficient level, as the table show that all (β eta) factors are significant on (Sig 0.000), and that insure there is positive and significant relationship between (FOA) and (AIS) Dimensions. also the Table (7) showed the test and results of simple regression of (R²) Adjusted R Square (R²), It swings between 0.522 to 0.505 in all variables and Dimensions of AIS, that mean the impact and the change in the AIS Accounting Information System dimensions variable was explained by FOA - forensic Accounting variables of (50%) percentage and the remain of percentage returned to other factor as result on random mistake,. While the F-test values (Mustafa et al., 2020), (KHALID, W. E et al., 2024). showed how affects the model's outcome variables which reflect Awareness of Forensic accounting is an effective tool for improving the efficiency of the accounting information system through the , System Quality ,Quality of service in the banking sector), and the F-values is Significant (0.000), additionally the Durbin-Watson (D.W) was used and Significant at the (0.05) level are swings between (2.0 - 2.3) it explain that there is no-relationship between mistake random of using Durbin-Watson, the result of regression showed that (all factors) are Significant, according to showed results the model approve . These exact values demonstrate how Forensic accounting and accounting information system dimensions relate, and these findings highlight the importance of Awareness of Forensic accounting is an effective tool for improving the efficiency of the accounting information system in the banking sector.

Testing Second- Third Hypothesis:

Regarding the second hypothesis (H.2: "Forensic Accounting contributes to improving the efficiency of AIS (system quality, service quality) to contain the damage resulting from financial crises (FCM) (containment/damage reduction FCM-CDR)") and the third hypothesis (H.3: "Forensic Accounting contributes to improving the efficiency of AIS (system quality and service quality) to restore activity after financial crises (recovery and restoration of activity FCM-RRA)"), Table (7) reveals the following:

Table 7: Test of Simple Regression between (FOA), (AIS), and (FCM)

FOA & AIS									
Variable	(R) Square	Adjusted (R) Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	(R) Square Change	Durbin-Watson	β eta	Sig	F Value	Sig
FCM-CDR	.727 ^a	.717	.74534	.727 ^a	2.090	.722	.000	3.721	.000 ^b
FCM-RRA	.724 ^a	.721	1.07705	.724 ^a	2.293	-.714	.000	3.943	.000 ^b

Source: Survey data, SPSS V23 -2024

The table indicates a positive and significant relationship between Forensic Accounting (FOA), Accounting Information Systems (AIS), and Financial Crisis Management (FCM) dimensions, with all (β) coefficients being significant on the level (Sig 0.000). This confirms a robust and significant association between FOA, AIS, and the various dimensions of FCM. Table (7) also presents the results of the simple regression analysis, including the Adjusted R-Square (R^2) values, which range from 0.724 to 0.727 across all variables and dimensions. These values suggest that approximately 70% of the variability in FCM dimensions can be attributed to the FOA and AIS factors. The remaining percentage is likely due to other factors or random error.

The F-test values demonstrated the impact of the model's outcome variables, confirming that forensic accounting significantly enhances the efficiency of the Accounting Information System (AIS) in both managing financial crises and restoring activities post-crisis. Specifically, forensic accounting contributes to improving AIS system quality and service quality for damage containment and reduction (FCM-CDR), as well as for recovery and restoration of activity (FCM-RRA), with the F-values being significant at Sig = 0.000. Additionally, the Durbin-Watson (D.W.) statistic, ranging from 2.0 to 2.3 and significant at the 0.05 level, indicates no significant autocorrelation in the residuals. This supports the validity of the regression model, suggesting that the observed results are not affected by random errors. Overall, the regression analysis confirms that all factors are significant and validates the model's effectiveness.

These specific values illustrate the relationships among forensic accounting, accounting information systems, and the dimensions of financial crises. The findings underscore the significance of forensic accounting as a crucial tool for enhancing the efficiency of accounting information systems in managing financial crises, particularly in terms of damage containment and reduction (FCM-CDR) and the recovery and restoration of activity following financial crises (FCM-RRA) within the banking sector. These results are consistent with the conclusions of studies by Verma and Sehgal (2016), Ghareb (2018), Alabaddi et al. (2020), and Dalloul et al. (2023).

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

A. Conclusions

This study addresses a significant gap in the literature by examining the interplay between forensic accounting, accounting information systems, and the financial crises impacting the banking sector. It focuses on the application of forensic accounting and its tools within the Sudanese banking environment, particularly in relation to the Bank of Khartoum, a leader in banking technology in Sudan. The study's relevance is highlighted by its exploration of forensic accounting's role in enhancing the efficiency of accounting information systems and its effectiveness in managing financial crises, particularly in the context of the April 15, 2023, war, which severely impacted the Sudanese banking system. Employing both descriptive and quantitative deductive approaches, the study used a structured questionnaire to gather data and assess the opinions of a targeted sample from the Bank of Khartoum. This sample comprised branch managers, department heads, financial controllers, systems analysts, and forensic accountants. The questionnaire was distributed electronically through the bank's semi-official channels and social media platforms, resulting in 254 completed surveys collected over a three-month period.

The study encountered challenges such as communication disruptions, intermittent internet services, job instability among bank employees, and the psychological impact of the ongoing conflict. Despite these difficulties, the sample size was deemed adequate. The descriptive and quantitative analysis revealed that none of the respondents were employed in forensic accounting roles or specialized in this field, nor was there a designated forensic accountant position within the bank's organizational structure. This lack of specialization indicates a limited focus on forensic accounting within the bank, highlighting an area for potential development.

The statistical analysis of the study yielded several significant findings, revealing a positive and statistically significant relationship between forensic accounting and the efficiency of the accounting information system. The data indicates that forensic accounting effectively enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of accounting systems,

particularly through its impact on the dimensions of system quality (SQ) and service quality (QS). Forensic accounting contributes by providing predictive and confirmatory information that addresses stakeholder needs, producing valuable reports, and supporting continuous updates to programs and systems used in financial and accounting tasks. Also, the impact of forensic accounting on systems and service quality is multifaceted. By focusing on accuracy, reliability, and proactive risk management, forensic accounting not only strengthens the integrity of accounting information systems but also enhances the overall service experience for clients. Expanding on these dimensions can provide deeper insights into how forensic accounting can be effectively integrated into banking operations, ultimately leading to improved resilience during financial crises and fostering long-term trust among stakeholders.

Furthermore, forensic accounting plays a crucial role in improving the efficiency of the accounting information system in managing financial crises. The study highlights that forensic accounting aids in two key phases of crisis management: containment and damage reduction (FCM-CDR), and recovery and restoration of activity post-crisis (FCM-RRA). According to the respondents, forensic accounting supports containment efforts, limits damage, and facilitates effective time management for implementing crisis recovery plans. It also assists in monitoring and analyzing practices leading to financial crises, assessing financial risks, and preparing for and preventing future crises. Additionally, it contributes to raising awareness about financial crises, efficiently storing, processing, and retrieving information, and identifying the necessary measures to restore normal bank operations following a crisis. The study found that the Bank of Khartoum successfully navigated the crisis due to its preparedness with alternative solutions, such as an independent power switch that ensured a stable power supply, and its ability to intermittently restore online systems to provide digital services, including bill payments and cash remittances. The bank also utilized financial technology, including mobile money transfers and electronic banking applications, and maintained a business continuity or disaster recovery plan. Despite these efforts, the study identified a lack of direct application of forensic accounting in addressing the current financial crisis. Although the bank possesses various forensic accounting tools and is working to restore services, there is a need for enhanced use of forensic accounting methods to effectively detect fraud and theft.

Overall, the study indicates that while there is a commitment to applying forensic accounting procedures, the direct application of forensic accounting within the Bank of Khartoum remains limited. This commitment is reflected in the operational departments and committees within the bank's organizational structure.

B. Recommendations:

Based on the statistical analysis, the study has affirmed that accounting information systems are vital in early detection of financial crises, devising potential plans and scenarios for managing and containing such crises, and supporting recovery efforts both during and after the crisis. These systems enhance the ability to generate reports and information critical for improving early warning mechanisms and crisis management strategies.

In light of these findings, the study recommends several key actions:

- ✓ There is a need to align forensic accounting practices with the quality and efficiency requirements of accounting information systems. This integration is essential for enhancing the production of reports and information that bolster early warning systems for financial crises and improve crisis management tasks at all stages—pre-crisis, during the crisis, and post-crisis.
- ✓ It is imperative to focus on increasing awareness among banking sector professionals about the importance of forensic accounting. This includes creating roles and providing training that support forensic accounting functions within the sector.
- ✓ Continued research efforts should aim to improve the characteristics of accounting and banking systems and expand their capacity to utilize forensic accounting tools effectively. This will help in managing financial crises more effectively.
- ✓ Developing standards for efficiency and effectiveness is crucial to enhance the relationship between forensic accounting and accounting information systems. This will contribute to better decision-making and performance.

- ✓ Invest in advanced forensic accounting software that integrates seamlessly with existing accounting information systems. This integration will enhance real-time monitoring, data analysis, and reporting capabilities, allowing for more effective fraud detection.
- ✓ Formulate and regularly update a crisis management plan that incorporates forensic accounting methodologies. Ensure that the plan outlines specific roles for forensic accountants in the phases of crisis containment, recovery, and restoration.

These recommendations aim to improve the effectiveness of accounting systems and forensic accounting practices in managing and mitigating the impact of financial crises.

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